

Contribution of Commercial Motorcyclists (Okada Riders) to the Dissemination of Community Acquired-Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (CA-MRSA) in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders) in Abakaliki, Nigeria, have been identified as potential reservoirs and disseminators of Community-Acquired Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (CA-MRSA) – an important public health concern. The detection of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) among commercial motorcycle operators (known as "Okada riders") in Ebonyi State, Nigeria was the aim of this study. We collected nasal swabs from 70 Okada riders at two locations: 30 from the Ebonyi State University Permanent Site (in Ohaukwu LGA) and 40 from the Margaret Umahi International Market (in Abakaliki LGA). MRSA was detected using Oxacilin and Cefoxitin disk testing methods, as per CLSI standards. It was observed from the result that the nasal colonisation of *S. aureus* among the Okada riders was 14(46.7%) and 31(77.5%) in EBSU permanent site and international market respectively. The overall prevalence of MRSA was 8(57.1%) and 13(41.9%) respectively in EBSU permanent site and international market. Community-acquired MRSA was found to be prevalent among commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders) in Abakaliki, indicating that this group may contribute significantly in the dissemination of MRSA within Abakaliki, Ebonyi State.

Keywords: Nasal colonisation, *Staphylococcus aureus*, Phenotypic detection, Methicillin resistance, Prevalence, Okada riders.

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Introduction

Staphylococcus aureus is versatile bacterium that is not only known as a commensal of human skin and mucosal, but also has frequently been associated with increased health outcome such as morbidity, mortality, and high treatment cost (Egwu et al., 2025; Cheung et

al., 2021). As pathogenic and commensal bacteria, *S. aureus* is capable of colonising and inhabiting the anterior nares of both humans and animals, including their groin, axillae, and gastrointestinal tracts (Shoib et al., 2023). However, the skin and the anterior nares are the most known reservoir of *S. aureus* and often serve as medium through which the bacterium

can easily spread to other important areas (Bode et al., 2010; Sivaraman et al., 2009). *S. aureus* has the capacity of establishing daunting interactions with the nasal epithelial cells. These they achieve by using different proteins and several other surface cell components (Mulcahy and McLoughlin, 2016). A report from Brown et al. (2014) has shown that *S. aureus* is capable of colonizing about 20 to 80 % of the anterior nares of human population. Therefore, the anterior nares of humans play important roles in both disease transmission and pathogenesis of *S. aureus*.

Consequently, MRSA is an important and critical group of Gram-positive bacteria with distinct genetics features, different from other strains of *S. aureus*. The unique attribute of this bacterium makes it an important public health concern. The pathogenesis of MRSA is quite unique and involves colonisation, adaptation, virulence with the help of few specialised virulence factors, before commencement of infection initiation followed by formation of abscess and lastly systemic infection (Shoab et al., 2023). Also, apart from a few virulence factors associated with *S. aureus* infection, it often contains several surface proteins referred to as microbial surface components recognising adhesive matrix molecules (MSCRAMMs). The MSCRAMMs usually binds to fibrinogen, fibronectin, and collagen fibers of host cells and enhance *S. aureus* ability to attack the surrounding host tissues (Menzies, 2003). Once the host's defense systems are destroyed by physical disruption or weakened due to diseases, colonisation therefore facilitates the establishment of infections (Wertheim et al., 2005). Generally, MRSA is a treacherous bacterium often resulting to multiple resistance index of antibiotics, partly due to its biofilm forming capability. All over the World, antimicrobial resistance has become major health concern especially in various healthcare facilities (Sakr et al., 2018; Fred, 2006), as it is often linked with treatment failure with great health outcome on the patients, caregiver and by extension-the physicians who spent more time for patient's treatment and looking for alternative treatment options. Within the community and even in the healthcare facilities, bacteria resistant strains including MRSA strains may pose serious health problems, as they have

the ability to easily spread out thus, creating wider infection control challenges to clinicians.

Following the stubborn intransigence of MRSA strains to chemotherapy and several disinfectants, they often pose a major threat to patient's overall healthcare and wellness (Slade et al., 2009). Prolonged therapy with methicillin may further complicate the treatment of patients and may further lead to development of low-level resistance which further compromise therapy which are not often detected by routine susceptibility diagnostic testing, commonly used in hospital laboratories (Tenover et al., 2004). *S. aureus* has been implicated in a wider range of infections, from acute to chronic infections and from mild to more serious infections such as boils, bacteriuria, osteomyelitis, pneumonia, endocarditis, meningitis, septicemia and arthritis. Understanding the prevalence and pathogenesis of MRSA is therefore important in controlling the menace due to MRSA.

While numerous studies have documented the nasal carriage of MRSA in hospital settings (Abdullahi et al., 2025; Egwu et al., 2025; Chen et al., 2012) and among high-risk groups like healthcare workers and in-patients (Adeiza et al., 2025; Akujobi et al., 2013; Udobi et al., 2013), there is a highly paucity of data regarding its prevalence within specific, high-contact community cohorts such as commercial motorcyclists in Nigeria. Commercial motorcyclists, known as Okada riders, represent a critical but understudied demographic. This is because, they are highly mobile, interact with a vast number of people daily, and often operate in environments with limited sanitation facilities, making them potential key reservoirs and disseminators of CA-MRSA within the community. However, the extent of MRSA nasal colonisation among this population in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, remains largely unknown. Thus, the need for this study, to bridge this gap by assessing their prevalence among commercial motorcyclists, known as Okada riders in Abakaliki.

Materials and Methods

Study Location

Ebonyi State University (EBSU) permanent site and Margaret Umahi International Market in Abakaliki L. G. A., both in Ebonyi State are the

two study location used. Ebonyi State University (EBSU) permanent site is located in Alioma Community of Ohaukwu L. G. A., Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Its specific coordinates are approximately 6.35° N and 8.05° E. The city is at the intersection of Enugu, Afikpo, and Ogoja roads. While, Margaret Umahi International Market is a first class Market located along Abakaliki -Ogoja Road on the West African Trans-sharan highway, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Its specific coordinates are approximately 6.3075° N and 8.1203° E. The international market is situated at the State capital and is the largest market in Ebonyi State. Both the whole sellers, retailers and other petty traders use the market to earn their livelihood. It is an everyday market with exception of Sundays.

Oral consent

Informed oral consent was obtained from commercial motorcycle operators (known as Okada riders) within the study area. The purpose and importance of the research were thoroughly explained to all participating riders. Furthermore, they were assured that the study's findings would be communicated to them upon completion. Only those who provided consent were recruited into the study, after which their samples were collected.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Available commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders) within the study locations who gave their consent to be part of this study were included in this study. While those who do not gave their consent were excluded from the study.

Collection of Sample

Exactly 70 nasal swab samples were aseptically collected from consenting commercial motorcycle operators (known as Okada riders) across two locations in Ebonyi State: thirty (30) samples were collected from riders operating within the permanent site of Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, located in Alioma Community, Ohaukwu Local Government Area; 40 samples were collected from riders operating within the Margaret Umahi International Market area. The sample collection procedure involved gently rotating a swab three times in a clockwise direction within the anterior nares of each

participant. Care was taken to ensure the swab tip reached the nasal ostium before the swab was covered. Following collection, all samples were transported to the Laboratory Unit of the Applied Microbiology Department, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, for subsequent analysis

Culture and bacterial isolation

In the laboratory, all the collected nasal swabs were first enriched on nutrient broth which was subjected to incubation at 37 °C for 24 hour prior to inoculation on Mannitol salt agar (MSA) for additional 24 hour at 37 °C. After overnight incubation, the preliminary identification of the culture plates was carried out by observing for colonies on the plates. All the colonies appearing golden yellow on the MSA were further subjected to different biochemical tests including coagulase and catalase tests, after being transferred onto nutrient agar, incubated overnight at 37 °C (Cheesbrough, 2010).

Preparation of 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard

The method as described by Cheesbrough, (2010) was followed in preparation.

Standardisation of test inoculum

The isolates were standardised using colony suspension methods (EUCAST, 2000) and as described by Olayinka and Onile (2009).

Antibiotics susceptibility testing (AST)

In detection of MRSA strains, Kirby and Bauer disc diffusion methods were followed. Accordingly, 24 hour colonies of the bacterium isolates which was initially cultured on a nutrient agar were sub-cultured onto sterile peptone water and incubated for 2 hours at 37 °C. The broth culture was further diluted to 0.5 McFarland turbidity equivalent standards. Using a sterile swab stick, the bacterium colony was streaked unto the surfaces of Mueller Hinton (MH) agar plates. Subsequently, sterile forceps was used to carefully place oxacillin (5-µg) and cefoxitin (30-µg) antibiotic discs, on the surface of the streaked MH agar, 15 mm apart from each other. The plates were allowed 30 mins for pre-diffusion, before they were inversely incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 24 hour. The inhibition zone diameters were measured using a calibrated meter rule and compared with Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI, 2015) guidelines.

Results

Colonial characteristics, Grams' reaction and biochemical features of the seventy (70) samples collected from the commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders) operating within EBSU Permanent site in Ohaukwu L.G.A. and Margaret Umahi International market of Abakaliki L.G.A revealed that the Okada riders harbors *S. aureus* in their anterior nares (Table 1).

Further analysis of the samples showed that the total prevalence of *S. aureus* nasal colonisation

of the commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders) operating within EBSU permanent site and the International market was 14(46.7%) and 31(77.5%) respectively (Table 2).

The result to detect MRSA colonising the anterior nares of the Okada riders showed that the isolated *S. aureus* harbored MRSA as the percentage resistance of the isolated *S. aureus* to cefoxitin and oxacillin antibiotics was 8(57.1%) and 13(41.9%) accordingly for commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders), operating within EBSU permanent site in Ohaukwu L.G.A. and Margaret Umahi International market (Table 3 and 4).

Table 1: Colonial morphology of *S. aureus* recovered from the nasals of apparently healthy commercial motor cycle operators (Okada riders) in Ohaukwu LGA

Colonial morphology	Grams Reaction	Catalase Test	Coagulase Test	Citrate test	Indole test	Isolated Bacteria
Colonies appeared round, smooth, golden yellow in colour on Mannitol salt agar	+	+	+	+	-	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>

Table 2: Percentage prevalence of *S. aureus* recovered from the nasals of apparently healthy commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders) in Ohaukwu LGA and International Market

Study location	Total number of samples collected (n =70)	Isolated bacteria	N(%) prevalence of <i>S. aureus</i> isolated from Okada riders
Ohaukwu L. G. A	30	<i>S. aureus</i>	14(46.7 %)
International Market	40		31 (77.5%)

Table 3: Methicillin resistance *S. aureus* (MRSA) from the nasals of apparently healthy commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders) in Ohaukwu LGA.

Antibiotics used (µg)	<i>S. aureus</i> isolates (N=14)	
	N(% susceptible)	N(% resistance)
FOX -30 µg	11(78.6)	3(21.4)
OX-5 µg	9(64.3)	5(35.7)
% prevalence of MRSA		8(57.1%)

Keys: FOX- 30µg = cefoxitin; OX-5µg = oxacillin

Table 4: Percentage of MRSA Recovered from Nasals of Commercial Motor Cycle Operators within International Market, Abakaliki

Antibiotics used (µg)	Frequency of <i>S. aureus</i> Isolation (n = 31)	% MRSA isolation
	n(% susceptible)	n(% resistance)
FOX -30 µg	27(87.0)	4(13.0)
OX-5 µg	22(71.0)	9(29.0)
% Prevalence of MRSA		13(41.9%)

Keys: FOX- 30µg = cefoxitin; OX-5µg = oxacillin

Fig. 1: MRSA (Resistance to ceftioxin and oxacillin) isolated from anterior nares of Okada riders in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State.

Discussion

Commercial motorcycle operators (Okada riders) in Abakaliki, Nigeria, have been identified as potential reservoirs and disseminators of Community-Acquired Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (CA-MRSA). Of the 30 nasal swabs collected from Okada riders within EBSU permanent site, the prevalence of *S. aureus* among the Okada riders was 14(46.7%), while the total prevalence of MRSA was 8(57.1%). The percentage prevalence 14(46.7%) of *S. aureus* observed in this study is found to be higher than 22(18.3%) *S. aureus* prevalence reported by Okwu et al. (2012). Also in the result of the study reported by Okwu et al. (2012), the MRSA percentage prevalence in their study was 13(10.8%) which is lower than 8(57.1%) MRSA prevalence observed in this study. However, the percentage prevalence of *S. aureus* observed in this study is in line with the report of percentage prevalence of *S. aureus* 40(33.3%) reported by Onanuga and Temedie, (2011). Also, the prevalence of nasal carriage of MRSA in the present study 8(57.1%), is also comparable with the results of previous similar study carried out among students from Taiwan

(19.3 %) and China (23.1 %), reported by Ma et al. (2011) and Chen et al. (2012) respectively. However, the variation expressed in the prevalence of nasal carriage of MRSA as revealed in this study and previous studies (Chen et al., 2012; Onanuga and Temedie, 2011; Ma et al., 2011) could be attributable to difference in geographical locations, environmental exposures, age differences, samples sizes as well as difference in infection control and prevention policies across countries. MRSA is recognized as one of the major causes of infections in humans, occurring in both the community and the hospital. It causes various skin infections, osteoarthritis, respiratory tract infections and other serious infections in the community (Okwu et al., 2012).

In the International market, the results of the analysis of 40 nasal swabs collected from the Okada riders showed that the prevalence of *S. aureus* was 31(77.5%). This result is consistence and comparable to other results of the prevalence of *S. aureus* reported internationally by several studies, such as 21% prevalence by Congdon et al. (2023); 69.8% prevalence by Blicharz et al. (2020) and 80.3% prevalence by Ukan et al. (2021). The difference

in the prevalence rate may also be associated with geographic location, age, number of representative samples etc. However, *S. aureus* strain is a known inhabitant of human and animal nose and may be responsible for several infections both in the hospital and in the community. Therefore, appropriate hand hygiene especially commercial motorcycle operators, keke operators, bus drivers and indeed all the transporters is important to reduce the menace of *S. aureus* infection.

Further analysis of the samples revealed that the prevalence of MRSA among the Okada riders operating within the international market was 13(41.9%). This percentage MRSA observed in this study is found to be higher but comparable to 19.0 % of MRSA reported by Jihong et al. (2024) in Beijing, China. However, 33(56.0%) MRSA prevalence was also reported by Ike et al. (2016) in Awka, Anambra, State, thus justifying the result of this present study. Behavioral conditions of this Okada people may be associated to the increased level of MRSA in this study, as most of these people are unexposed individuals, uneducated and lacks basic knowledge of hygiene.

Furthermore, the high density of people and frequent physical contact with passengers and cash at the International Market could facilitate the transmission of *S. aureus*. Also, lack of access to handwashing facilities at their various parks could be a critical factor hindering hand hygiene- a known key intervention for reducing staphylococcal transmission (Genc and Arikan, 2020; Lederer et al., 2009). Failure to regularly wash their hands or use hand rubs/sanitizers regularly even after their hectic work each day may have also contributed to increased resistance rate of the isolated *S. aureus*, thus resulting to increased MRSA prevalence in this study.

The high prevalence of MRSA among Okada riders, particularly in the densely populated International Market and the University community, suggests that this occupational group may be a significant reservoir for CA-MRSA in Abakaliki. This is concerning because these individuals who are often exposed to MRSA through contact with the riders will also serve as an agent for transmission of MRSA among other members of the community.

Conclusion

The anterior nares of commercial Okada riders in Abakaliki harbored MRSA from which they can be disseminated to other areas and from persons to persons, leading to CA-MRSA. The finding calls for behavioral change of these Okada riders and a call to institute an antibiotic usage policy in Nigeria to checkmate the abuse of antibiotics and other substance which may be a predisposing factor to MRSA. Also there is need to establish and monitor hand hygiene protocol in all the parks of these Okada riders to reduce the transmission of the pathogen.

References

- Abdullahi, S., Abdullahi, I. N., Adekola, H. A., Baamlong, N., Dangana, A., Usman, Y., Ahmad, A. E., Salisu, S. and Abdulaziz, M. M. (2025). Nasal carriage rate and multiple antimicrobial resistance indices of *Staphylococcus aureus* among healthcare students at the Ahmadu Bello University, Nigeria. *Afr. J. Lab. Med*, 14(1): 2667. doi: 10.4102/ajlm.v14i1.2667.
- Adeiza, S. S., Onaolapo, J. A. and Olayinka, B. O. (2020). Prevalence, risk-factors, and antimicrobial susceptibility profile of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) obtained from nares of patients and staff of Sokoto state-owned hospitals in Nigeria. *GMS Hyg Infect Control*, 12(15): 1-17. doi: 10.3205/dgkh000360.
- Akujobi, C. N., Ilo, I. A., Egwuatu, C. C. and Ezeanya, C. C. (2013). Prevalence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) among healthcare workers in a tertiary institution in Nigeria. *OJM*, 25(3-4): 82-87.
- Blicharz, L., Usarek, P., Młynarczyk, G., Skowroński, K., Rudnicka, L. and Samochocki, Z. (2020). Nasal colonization by staphylococci and severity of atopic dermatitis. *Dermatitis*, 31: 215–222.
<https://doi:10.1097/DER.0000000000000568>.
- Bode, L. G. M., Kluytmans, J. A. J. W., Wertheim, H. F. L., Bogaers, D., Vandenbroucke-Grauls, C. M. J. E. and Roosendaal, R. (2010). Preventing surgical-site infections in nasal carriers of *Staphylococcus aureus*. *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 362: 9–17.
<https://doi:10.1056/NEJMoa0808939>.

- Brown, A. F., Leech, J. M., Rogers, T. R. and McLoughlin, R. M. (2014). *Staphylococcus aureus* colonization: modulation of host immune response and impact on human vaccine design. *Front. Immunol.*, 4: 507. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2013.00507>.
- Cheesebrough M. (2010). District laboratory practice in tropical countries. Cambridge University Press, New York, Pp. 157-164.
- Chen, C. S., Chen, C. Y. and Huang, Y. C. (2012). Nasal carriage rate and molecular epidemiology of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* among medical students at a Taiwanese university. *Int. J. Infect. Dis.*, 16(11): 799–803.
- Cheung, G. Y. C., Bae, J. S. and Otto, M. (2021). Pathogenicity and virulence of *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Virulence*, 12(1):547-569. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21505594.2021.1878688>
- Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI). (2015). Performance standard for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. twentyfifth informational supplement, CLSI document M100-S20, Wayne, PA.
- Egwu, I. H., Egwu-Ikechukwu, M. M., Amaechi-Nnaji, V. O. and Nwaeze, O. (2025). Effect of selected antiseptics liquids sold in Abakaliki metropolis against *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from medical students and hospital equipment in a tertiary care hospital, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 3(7): 3594-3603. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16447543>
- European Committee for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST). (2000). Determination of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of antibacterial agents by agar dilution, *Clin. Microbiol. Infect.*, 6: 509–515.
- Fred, C. (2006). Mechanism of antimicrobial resistance in bacteria. *Am. J. Med.*, 119(6): 55–510.
- Genc, O. and Arikan, I. (2020). The relationship between hand hygiene practices and nasal *Staphylococcus aureus* carriage in healthcare workers. *Med Lav.*, 111(1): 54-62. doi: 10.23749/mdl.v111i1.8918.
- Ike, B., Ugwu, M. C., Ikegbunam, M. N., Nwobodo, D., Ejikeugwu, C., Gugu, T. and Esimone, C. O. (2016). Prevalence, antibiogram and molecular characterization of community-acquired methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in AWKA, Anambra Nigeria. *Open Microbiol. J.*, 10: 211-221
- Ikeh, E. I. (2003). Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) at Jos teaching hospital. *Afr J Clin Exp Microbiol*, 4(1):52-55.
- Jihong, G., xiong, M., Zhang, J. and Li, Y. (2024). Prevalence and characterization of community associated *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from human mastitis in Beijing, China. *Int. J. Med. Microbiol.*, 315:151623.
- Lederer, J. W. J., Best, D. and Hendrix, V. (2009). A comprehensive hand hygiene approach to reducing MRSA health care-associated infections. *Jt Comm J Qual Patient Saf*, 35(4):180-5. doi: 10.1016/s1553-7250(09)35024-2.
- Ma, X. X., Sun, D. D., Wang, S., Wang, M. L., Li, M., Shang, H., Wang, E. H. and Luo, E. J. (2011). Nasal carriage of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* among preclinical medical students: epidemiologic and molecular characteristics of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* clones. *Diagn Microbiol Infect Dis*, 70(1): 22–30.
- Menzies, B. E. (2003). The role of fibronectin binding proteins in the pathogenesis of *Staphylococcus aureus* infections. *Curr Opin. Infect. Dis.*, 16: 225–229.
- Mulcahy, M. E. and McLoughlin, R. M. (2016). Host-bacterial crosstalk determines *Staphylococcus aureus* nasal colonization. *Trends Microbiol*, 24: 872–886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2016.06.012>.
- Okwu, M., Bamgbala, S. and Aborisade, W. (2012). Prevalence of nasal carriage of community-associated methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (CA-MRSA) among healthy primary school children in Okada, Nigeria. *J. Nat. Sci. Res*, 2(4): 61-67.

- Olayinka, A. T. and Onile, B. A. (2009). Bacterial use of antibiotics/antimicrobial agents, Nigerian medical practitioners. *Int. J. Med. Med. Sci.*, 33: 79-82
- Onanuga, A. and Temedie, T. C. (2011). Nasal carriage of multi-drug resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in healthy inhabitants of Amassoma in Niger Delta region of Nigeria. *Afr. Health Sci.*, 11(2): 176 – 181
- Sakr, A., Brégeon, F., Mège, J. L., Rolain J-M. and Blin, O. (2018) *Staphylococcus aureus* Nasal Colonization: An update on mechanisms, epidemiology, risk factors, and subsequent infections. *Front. Microbiol.*, 9: 2419. <https://doi:10.3389/fmicb.2018.02419>
- Shoaib, M., Aqib, A. I., Muzammil, I., Majeed, N., Bhutta, Z. A., Kulyar, M. F., Fatima, M., Zaheer, C. F., Muneer, A., Murtaza, M., Kashif, M., Shafqat, F. and Pu, W. (2023). MRSA compendium of epidemiology, transmission, pathophysiology, treatment, and prevention within one health framework. *Front. Microbiol.*, 10;13:1067284. <https://doi:10.3389/fmicb.2022.1067284>
- Sivaraman, K., Venkataraman, N. and Cole, A. M. (2009). *Staphylococcus aureus* nasal carriage and its contributing factors. *Future Microbiol.*, 4: 999–1008. <https://doi:10.2217/fmb.09.79>
- Slade, D., Lindner, A. B., Paul, G. and Radman M. (2009). Recombination and replication in DNA repair of heavily irradiated *Deinococcus radiodurans*. *cell*, 136: 1044-1055.
- Tenover, F. C., Weigel, L. M. and Appelbaum, P. C. (2004). Vancomycin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolation from a patient in Renssylvania. *J Antimicrob Agents Chemother*, 48: 275-280.
- Udobi, C. E., Obajuluwa, A. F. and Onaolapo, J. A. (2013). Prevalence and antibiotic resistance pattern of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from an orthopaedic hospital in Nigeria. *BioMed Res Int*, 2013: 1-4. doi: 10.1155/2013/860467.
- Ukan, M., Jamil, H., Bokhari, H. A., Khattak, A. A., Khan, A. N. and Ullah, Z. (2021). Nasal carriage of highly resistant methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains by hospital staff in hazara region of pakistan. *J. Pak. Med. Assoc.*, 71:47–50. <https://doi:10.47391/JPMA.177>.
- Wertheim, H. F., Melles, D. C., Vos, M. C., van Leeuwen, W., van Belkum, A., Verbrugh, H. A. and Nouwen, J. L. (2005). The role of nasal carriage in *Staphylococcus aureus* infections. *Lancet Infect Dis*, 5: 751-762.